

A Review on the Pregnancy Induced Gingival Enlargement: Pyogenic Granuloma

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Abstract:

Gingivitis refers to the inflammation of gingiva but with attachment loss. The gingiva is called as inflamed when it do had all the signs of inflammation such as rubor, dolor, calor, pain, and loss of function. In some cases the gingiva becomes enlarged in size, a term called as gingival hyperplasia. Gingival hyperplasia can be caused by a variety of conditions some are specific and some are non specific. These non specific conditions are those in which their exact mechanism of the systemic conditioning factor had not been identified. One of such conditioned gingival enlargement is pyogenic granuloma which is caused by the exaggregated response to minor trauma whose mechanism of exaggregation is not identified. However despite being a non specific conditioned gingival enlargement, Pyogenic granuloma is most common in a pregnant women because of the high rise of hormonal level. It appears as an exophytic reddish or reddish bluish discrete, isolated, spherical tumor like mass with or without a peduncle. The main treatment modality is the surgical excision of the granuloma, however other treatment modalities such as by Laser, cryotherapy, electrocautery are also available. The main aim of writing this review is to make the clinician aware of the diagnosis, differential diagnosis, and various treatment modalities that are available to treat the pyogenic granuloma.

Key Words: Enlargement, Pregnancy, pyogenic granuloma, treatment, recurrence.

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Introduction:

Periodontology is a speciality of dentistry, that deals with the structures around the teeth. Hereby these structures are divided into two categories.

1. Gingiva: whose main function is the protection of the underlying structures, and these underlying structures are known as the supporting structures which hold the tooth in their socket. These supporting structures are called as periodontal ligament, cementum, and alveolar bone. Based upon this classification, two types of disease are of utmost concern in the field of Periodontology i.e. gingivitis, and Periodontitis. The main difference between gingivitis and periodontitis is based upon the fact, that in gingivitis there is an inflammation of gingiva but without

the extension of this inflammation into bone, and hence no bone loss, and clinical attachment loss. When this inflammation get extend from gingiva into bone, then the bone loss and clinical attachment loss occurs, then this condition is called as periodontitis.¹ Since gingivitis term is derived as in gingivi meaning gingiva, and this means inflammation. So since its an inflammation of gingiva, and inflammation has its own 5 cardinal signs that is rubor (redness), calor (heat), dolor (pain), swelling, and, loss of function.² In some cases of gingivitis there is also an increase in the size of gingiva a condition known as gingival hyperplasia or hypertrophic gingivitis, which now had been replaced by the term gingival enlargement or gingival overgrowth.³

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Classification of gingival enlargement

A. Based upon the etiologic factors, and pathologic changes:³

1. Inflammatory enlargement:

- a. Acute
- b. Chronic

2. Drug induced enlargement³

- a. Anticoagulants(Phenytoin)
- b. Immunosuppressants(Cyclosporine)
- c. Calcium Channel Blockers (Nifedipine)

3. Enlargement associated with systemic disease and conditions³

A. Specific Conditioned Enlargement

- a. Pregnancy
- b. Puberty
- c. Nutritional Deficiency
- d. Plasma cell Gingivitis

B. Non-specific conditioned enlargement

- a. Pyogenic Granuloma

C. Systemic Diseases causing gingival enlargement³

- a. Leukemia
- b. Wegners Granulomatosis, sarcoidosis

4. Neoplastic enlargement³

- a. Benign
- b. Malignant

5. False enlargement

B. On the basis of location and distribution.³

1. **Localized:** Limited to a gingiva adjacent to a single teeth or a group of teeth.
2. **Generalized:** Involving the gingiva throughout the mouth.
3. **Marginal:** Confined to the marginal gingiva.
4. **Papillary:** Confined to the interdental papilla.
5. **Diffuse:** Involving the marginal gingiva, attached gingiva, and the papillary gingiva
6. **Discrete:** An isolated sessile or pedunculated tumor like gingival enlargement.

C. Based upon the scoring of gingival enlargement³

1. Grade 0: No signs of gingival enlargement.
2. Grade 1: Enlargement confined to the interdental papilla.
3. Grade 2: Enlargement involves papilla and marginal gingiva.
4. Grade 3: Enlargement covers three quarters or more of the crown.

Historical background of Pyogenic granuloma

The term pyogenic granuloma is derived from a word pyo means pus, and granuloma means granuloma. The first case of pyogenic granuloma was noticed by Hullihen. Pyogenic granuloma in man was firstly described in 1897 and was called by the term Botryomycosis hominis. Later on this term changed to pyogenic granuloma by Hartzell in 1904 and is so in the present use till date. As on the term was discovered by Hartzell, so pyogenic granuloma is also known by the name Crocker and Hartzell's disease. Because of the histological characteristic of pyogenic granuloma as the presence of numerous blood vessels, and the inflammatory nature of the lesion, Angelopolus called it as hemangiomaticus granuloma.⁴

Etiology of Pyogenic Granuloma

As per the different investigators, pyogenic granuloma has different etiologies. Some of the investigators believe that the formation of pyogenic granuloma in the oral cavity and the skin can be because of low grade physical trauma, hormonal factors, while the another investigators believe it to be because of bacterial, virus or fungal infection, or because of certain drugs. In the oral cavity, particularly gingiva is the commonly affected site, approx. in 75% of the cases. The main etiology in the gingiva can be because of plaque, calculus, foreign body, and poor oral hygiene.⁵

Characteristics feature of pyogenic granuloma

- **Appearance-** Pyogenic granuloma in the oral cavity appears as an slow growing, painless, asymptomatic, elevated, exophytic, sessile or pedunculated growth.⁶
- **Colour-** depending upon the vascularity, the color ranges from reddish to reddish purplish, to pink.⁶
- **Gingival site-** the most common part of gingiva affected is the marginal gingiva of the mandibular anterior tooth region and mostly the labial surface.⁶
- **Size-** Varies from few millimetres to centimetres⁶

Fig 1: Clinical photo of pyogenic granuloma in a 28 years pregnant patient.

Pregnancy and Pyogenic Granuloma

Though pyogenic granuloma is a non specific conditioned enlargement, but it is more common in pregnancy because of the following reasons:⁷

1. A three fold increase in the level of estrogen and progesteron or called as an harmonal imbalance may lead to a frequent irritation response such that the pregnancy gingivitis (which is essential for pyogenic granuloma to develop), gets converted to localized gingival enlargement.⁷
2. The high level of estrogen and progesterone leads to the changes in the structure and the function of lymphatics and blood vessels as a result there is an increased in the vascular response leading to pyogenic granuloma.⁷
3. The elevated level of these sex harmones exerts various biological and immunological changes on various growth factors particularly fibroblast growth factor,as a result of which there is a heavy production of fibroblast leading to growth of this granulomatous tissue.⁷
4. The high rise of progesterone in the gingival tissues of preganent lady leads to the suppression of acute inflammatory reaction against plaque but an initiation of chronic tissue reaction,leading to the growth of the pyogenic granuloma.⁷

Histopathological features of pyogenic granuloma

1. Histopathological picture of pyogenic granuloma shows the proliferation of blood vessels which resemble the granulation tissue.⁸
2. Blood vessels are arranged in clusters or a medullary pattern often separated by a less or avascular fibrotic septa,so because of this reason,the pyogenic granuloma is often considered a form of capillary haemangioma.⁸
3. Fibroblast has a plump shape and the stromal cells shows a mitotic activity.
4. Some scarring is present in the granulation tissue,which indicates the maturation of connective tissue repair process.⁸
5. The surface of the tissue show some secondary nonspecific changes which include capillary dilation, stromaledema, inflammation, and granulation tissue reaction.⁸
6. Tissue surface show ulcerations and is replaced by a purulent thick fibrous membrane.⁸
7. Tissue shows a mixture of inflammatory cell infiltrate, where the neutrophils are found in superficial layer of ulcerated surface ,and chronic inflammatory cells are found in the deeper layers of the ulcerated surface.⁸
8. Two histopathological forms of pyogenic granuloma can be seen⁸

A. Lobular Capillary haemangioma- It shows that the arrangement of blood vessels is in a lobule and the blood vessels does not go any significant changes like dilation, stromaledema, or inflammatory tissue reaction.

B. Non lobular capillary haemangioma- characterized by a greater proliferation of blood vessels along with highly significant changes like vascular dilation, stromaledema, and inflammatory tissue reaction and a greater resemblance to granulation tissue.

Pyogenic granuloma a misnomer

As the term pyogenic granuloma came into existence,so many investigators that that pyogenic granuloma means a pus producing granulomatous lesion. But when the histological investigations were carried out,so it came into existence that the term pyogenic granuloma doesnot dedicate to terms as whats in its name,infact it become clear histologically that it is not associated with pus and more commonly resemble an angiomatous lesion rather than the granulomatous lesion. Also clinically on the basis of etiology, it is an hyperplastic response of the gingival tissue to the harmonal imbalance in a preganent lady showing that its not an actual tumor (as its not because of any infection),but of course a tumor like enlargement clinically.⁹

Differential diagnosis of pyogenic granuloma

When any growth is found in the oral cavity, then it becomes an important concern to differentiate one growth from other, as this may not only help in the proper diagnosis of the growth, but also help us to decide a correct treatment. These growth that shows clinical resemblance to each other must be differentiated histologically and then again should be correlated clinically. The following can be the differential diagnosis of the pyogenic granuloma on clinical and histopathological basis:¹⁰

1. Peripheral giant cell granuloma vs Pyogenic Granuloma¹⁰

Peripheral Giant Cell Granuloma	Pyogenic granuloma
More bluish purple in color (Less differentiating feature)	More bright red in color.
Appearance of multinucleated giant cells (high differentiating feature)	Appearance of more proliferating & dilated blood vessels
Lack of infectious source	Non-specific infectious source.

2. Peripheral ossifying fibroma vs pyogenic granuloma¹⁰

Peripheral ossifying fibroma	Pyogenic granuloma
Lighter in color	More dark in color
Size can be about 1.5 to 6 cm	Size is 1 to 2.5 cm but rarely exceeds more than 2.5 cm.
Found exclusively on the gingiva	Found on gingiva in most of the cases but can also be found on tongue and lip.
Minimum vascular component	Maximum vascular component

3. Metastatic cancer vs pyogenic granuloma¹⁰

Metastatic cancer	Pyogenic granuloma
Attached gingiva is the most commonly affected site and the other site is the tongue.	Marginal gingiva is the most commonly affected site.
Most commonly diagnosed in fifth to seventh decade	Most commonly diagnosed in the second decade.

Treatment of pyogenic granuloma

Treatment of pyogenic granuloma depends upon the size of the lesion, the consistency of the lesion, bleeding tendency, etiologic factors. In a pregnant women, considering all these factors at a time is difficult, therefore in most of the cases, treatment depends upon the control of etiologic factors, and a good practice of oral hygiene measures. However, if there is a severe pain, difficulty in mastication, then apart from control of etiologic factors, surgical excision is the treatment of choice in the second trimester. However in order to avoid the bleeding tendency and to provide a good pain control (which to some extent cannot be achieved by a conventional scalpel technique), various other treatment options are available which can be described as follows:

- 1. Laser:** Lasers are known for their good bleeding control and less intraoperative and postoperative pain however a delayed healing by laser as compared to scalpel. Two types of Laser are available, CO₂ Laser, and Nd:Yag Laser. However Nd:Yag laser is a better choice as the coagulation property of Nd:Yag laser are better than the coagulation tendency of CO₂ Laser.¹¹
- 2. Cryosurgery:** Good option as it gives an excellent esthetic results.¹¹

3. Absolute Ethanol Injection: Less invasive therapy than Cryosurgery.¹¹

4. Sclerotherapy: it uses the injection of sodium tetradecyl sulfate and a multiple sessions of it, but with absolute no scarring.¹¹

Recurrence rate of pyogenic granuloma

Recurrence rate of pyogenic granuloma in pregnancy varies from 8% to 16%. The clinical significance of recurrence rate in pregnancy is based upon the fact that because of three fold hormonal rise in pregnancy, if the pyogenic granuloma is excised during pregnancy, then there would be a chance of recurrence and hence the excision treatment must be carried out after parturition. But because the hormonal condition regress back to normal after pregnancy so there can be a high chance that the pyogenic granuloma might get regress after pregnancy, eliminating the need of surgical intervention.¹²

Conclusion

Gingival enlargement is the result of various conditions. Some are the local conditions restricted to the oral cavity, while some are the systemic conditions which can be physiological and pathological which can lead to gingival enlargement. One of the systemic physiological condition is pregnancy, during which there is an increase in level of hormones estrogen and progesterone. As a result of this increase in the sex hormones, the effect is sometimes seen on the gingiva in the form of enlargement, which can either be generalized, and in most of the cases isolated single growth. One such isolated single growth is the pyogenic granuloma, which is particularly a non-specific conditioned enlargement but is more common in a specific conditioned enlargement that is pregnancy. The reason for this common condition in pregnancy is because of the various effects like the changes in structure and function of blood vessels and lymphatics, excessive activation of fibroblast growth factor, and a chronic tissue reaction towards the irritants by these hormones. Though the term pyogenic granuloma is a misnomer as its not a pus producing lesion, and more an angiomatous lesion rather than a granulomatous lesion. Various treatment modalities are available like surgical excision by scalpel, Laser, sclerotherapy, cryosurgery, absolute ethanol injection and the use of these treatment modalities depend upon the clinical condition of the pyogenic granuloma. The treatment of pyogenic granuloma in pregnancy may varies from control of the etiological factors to surgical excision to no treatment at all as it all depends upon the interference with mastication, pain, bleeding tendency up to the regression of pyogenic granuloma after pregnancy.

References

1. Newman M, Takei H. Klokkevold P, Carranza F. Carranza's Clinical Periodontology. Second South Asia Edition.
2. Newman M, Takei H. Klokkevold P, Carranza F. Carranza's Clinical Periodontology. Tenth Edition.
3. Harshmohan. Textbook of Pathology. Eight Edition.
4. Hartzell MB (1904). Granuloma Pyogenicam. J Cutan Dis Syph 22,520-525.
5. Kamal R,Daliya P, Puri A. Oral Pyogenic granuloma: Various Concepts of etiopathogenesis. J Oral Maxillofac Pathol.2012 Jan-Apr;16(1): 79-82.
6. RegeziJA,ScuibaJJ,Jordim RCK (2003) Oral Pathology: Clinical Pathologic Considerations. 4thed,WB Saunders,Philadelphia,115-116.
7. MussalliNG,HoppasRM,Johnson NW(1976). Oral pyogenic granuloma as a complication of pregnancy and the use of hormonal Contraceptives. Int J GynaecolObstrtt 104,187-191.
8. Kapadia SB, Heffner DK (1992) Pitfalls in the histopathologic diagnosis of Pyogenic Granuloma. Eur Arch Otorhinolaryngol 249,195-200.
9. Eversole CR (2002). Clinical outline of Oral Pathology: Diagnosis and treatment. 3rd Edition.
10. Sonis ST, FazioRc, Fang LST (1995) Principles and Practice of Oral Medicine 2nd edition, WB Saunders, Philadelphia,416.
11. Greenley MS, Glich M (2003), Burketts Oral Medicine: Diagnosis and treatment,10th Edition. BC Decker, Hemilton, 113-114.
12. Debnath K, Chatterjee A. Management of Recurrent Pyogenic Granuloma with platelet Rich Fibrin. J Indian Soc Periodontal.2018 July-Aug;22(4): 360-364.

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